

Supplemental Methods

Cell viability study

Cell viability studied by Cell Counting Kit-8 assay (CCK-8; Dojindo Laboratory, Japan) as previously described (3). Briefly, cells were prepared to 96-wells (SPL, Korea). After LPS treatment in various indicate dose and incubate for 24 h, replace 100 μ l of serum free media and 10 μ l of CCK-8 solution for 2 h. The absorbance (450 nm) was measured with a Synergy 2 microplate reader (BioTek).

Reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR)

RT-PCR with RNA isolation and generation of cDNA was performed as described previously (2). Briefly, total cellular RNA was isolated with an RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), then cDNA was synthesized from 2 μ g of total RNA using an oligo-dT primer and Superscript IV reverse transcriptase enzyme (Invitrogen) in a final volume of 20 μ l at 55°C according to the manufacturer's instructions. The forward primer of TLR4 is 5'-GTGGGTCAAGGACCAGAAAA-3', and the reverse primer is 5'-GCAATGGCTACACCAGGAAT-3'. The forward primer of GAPDH is 5'-CCATCTTCCAGGAGCGAGAT-3', and the reverse primer is 5'-AAGACGCCAGTAGACTCCAC-3'. The previously reported primers were also used (1, 4, 6) The following primer sequences were used: Na⁺/K⁺/2Cl⁻ forward, 5'-GTCAGCCATACCCAAAGGAA-3'; reverse, 5'-GGAGACTTTGCAAGTGACG-3'. Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α forward, 5'-CCGGAATTCTGCCTTCCCCTACTCCCTTCT-3'; reverse, 5'-TGCTCTAGACTTCCCCGCTGTCGTCGCCGTCAC-3'. Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase β forward, 5'-GTTCGAATTCCCTCCGTCCTAATGACCCCA-3'; reverse, 5'-GCG GGA TCC GAC CAGAGCAGTTCCCCAGCCAGTCAGA-3'. α ENaC forward, 5'-

TGATCAAGAAGTGTGGCTGTG-3'; reverse, 5'-CCGGCAGAGAGTTTGTAGTTG-3'.
 Ano1 forward, 5'-GAACGTGACGAGGATACCAAA-3'; reverse, 5'-
 AGACTATTGTGCTCCGGGTTT-3'. CFTR forward, 5'-
 GTCTCCAGAGGACCAGAGCTT-3'; reverse, 5'-TCTGAAGAGGCTCAGAGCAAG-3'.

The conditions of a PCR amplification were as described previously (5). PCR products were resolved by using Mupid-2 plus electrophoresis system (OPTIMA, Tokyo, Japan) on 1.2 % agarose gels containing 0.1 µg/mL ethidium bromide (Sigma Aldrich) and were visualized under UV light with a transilluminator (TS-312R; Spectroline, Westbury, NY, USA).

References

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